

**COGNITIVE ASPECTS IN THE JUSTAPOSITION OF IMAGES IN
ONDINE, FROM THE WORK GASPAR DE LA NUIT BY MAURICE
RAVEL**

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Introduction

The purpose of this communication is to demonstrate , through a vertical montage of the piece *Ondine* from the work *Gaspar de la Nuit* by Maurice Ravel, cognitive aspects of the sound events present in the musical discourse translated into a cast of images that reflect the character of these same events . We *present* excerpts from *Ondine* with film excerpts and graphic images corresponding to the ideas that the piece evokes, trying to understand how the gesture, sound, image, among other possible aspects, constitute the mental representation of the music witnessed. For the choice of images, the following were considered: ideas contained in the poem by Aloysius Bertrandt (1842) that inspired Ravel to compose the piece; sound design (rhythmic and melodic contours, harmonics and other musical elements); the movements performed by the pianist when playing the piece. In this part of the research, we take as a reference part of the cinema literature that deals with the relationship between sound and image (Eisenstein 2010).

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Structure and Methodology

The work was structured in three parts: 1. Introduction to the play and poem based on Orenstein (1989) and Benedetti (2011); 2. considerations on sound and image in vertical montage ⁸and cognitive aspects of the mental representation of music, using some works by Eisenstein (2002; 2010), Souza (2005) and Godinho (2005). 3. vertical montage of the piece, where we take the ideas from the poem, the sound design and the execution movements and associate them with the images.

Undine is a descriptive work. There are many evidences of the close relationship between music and poem. Among the most notable we mention the movement of the waters described by the ostinato XYXXYXXY (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Ostinato – Representation of moving water. *Undine* (c. 1-10). Ravel, *Gaspar de la Nuit* (1909)

Undine 's subtle singing (Figure 2) is portrayed by *legato* writing and indications *pp* and *très doux* , where the hand movements when performing the indications communicate the character of lightness and softness, as if the song were emerging from the depths of the waters.

Figure 2: Song of *Undine* . *Undine* (c. 3, 4). Ravel, *Gaspar de la Nuit* (1909)

⁸In film literature, vertical montage refers to the juxtaposition of sound with image .

The climax of the piece (Figure 4) , between measures 67 and 70, coincides with the moment of greater technical and pianistic complexity:

Figure 3 : Climax. *Undine* (c. 67-70). Ravel, *Gaspar de la Nuit* (1909)

When dealing with the relationship between sound and image, we sought to meet what Eisenstein (2002) says about image and its internal representation. According to him, the image enters our consciousness and perception, along with its details that are preserved in sensations and memory as parts of a whole. Such details will be concatenated in the total image that accumulates these same isolated elements. Based on this idea, our intention was to perceive in music the parts of the whole that find meaning when connected as a whole.

For Eisenstein (2010), a work of art in its dynamic aspect is the process of organizing images in the viewer's senses and mind. We believe that this is possible, and that the impression and potentiality of ordering the images in this way is greater, as more than one art works for the same purpose. For Godinho (2005, p. 362):

Music is inevitably the classroom entity next door, but it never stops gesturing in our minds. What we hear allows us to mentally reconstitute a body with movement, gestures and postures, with a certain intentionality, a certain attitude or a certain emotional state.

With this, it is clear that gesture, sound, image, among other possible aspects, form the mental representation of the music witnessed. According to Souza (2005, p. 127), the representation of music in our mind is a multifaceted set of images, which includes auditory and visual information, as well as tactile and motor information involved and collected during

musical experiences. All this information constitutes the mental imagery of the music insofar as it consolidates relationships between them. Based on these relationships, we perceive the possibility of using certain images throughout *Ondine*, whose degree of adequacy to the musical discourse would be greater as they come into line with the mental representation constituted by the mentioned aspects. Alongside this, with equal importance, we take into account the literary environment as a support for understanding the ideas communicated in sound.

Results

Starting from the mental representation of the musical discourse constructed by visual, auditory, tactile and motor information, we searched for dynamic images (excerpts from films) that corresponded to this representation. In the vertical assembly of the piece (third stage), the film excerpts were juxtaposed with *Ondine*'s music performed by the author. Below are the film images that illustrate the most significant moments of the play, accompanied by a description of the relationship they present with musical aspects and performance engines.

In Figure 4, the trembling of the waters reflecting the moonlight in the image was related to the trembling of the right hand that performs the 'XYXXYXXY' *ostinato*. The veiled and mysterious song of *Ondine* that emerges from the depths of the waters, present in her left hand, was related to the woman's face partially hidden in the mist:

Lento
PPP (sempre legato)

Para a realização deste ostinato, o movimento da mão consiste em um tremular, resultante da alternância entre sol suspenso e lá natural. Este tremular vai ao encontro do calmo filitar das águas, proposto pelo poema e evocado pelo som.

très doux et très expressif

Os movimentos que a mão esquerda realiza para cantar a melodia, mantendo o legato, a condução e intensidade adequadas, evocam ideia de tranquilidade e leveza. Quase como um dançar sobre as águas.

Figure 4: Scene from the films *Aurora* by Murnau (1927) and *Coeur Fidèle* by Epstein (1923).

In figure 5 we have the moment of virtuosic apotheosis and of maximum intensity and expansion of the sound space. The movements used in the execution complete the furious character of this thunderous passage. The film images portray the same information perceived

from the auditory, motor and graphic aspect of the score, but with the characteristics of cinematographic art.

Figure 5: Scene from *The Raging Sea* .

Final considerations

We saw that the images from the films chosen and juxtaposed to the music respond to a mental image that is constituted by auditory, visual, tactile and motor experience. The main musical idea, taken from the literary work in question, is likely to be expressed in sound, movement, spelling and even in the visual aspect resulting from the motor action of execution. The intersection between these areas brings us closer to a greater understanding of how our understanding appropriates the musical narrative, in this case, of a broadly descriptive nature. Such an approximation is quite enriching for the interpretation and contributes to its improvement and development, since it points to aspects through which information is transmitted and to the way in which these same aspects are stimulated.

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FILMS:

AURORA. Directed by Friedrich Wilhelm Murnau. USA: William Fox, 1927.

COEUR Fidele. Directed by Jean Epstein. Paris: Cinématèque Française, 1923.

THE PERFECT STORM. Directed by Wolfgang Petersen. New York: Warner Bros., 2000.